

MULTISCALE CO-ROTATIONAL METHOD FOR GEOMETRIC NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF HETEROGENEOUS PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE

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Keywords: Piezoelectric Composite, Heterogeneous, Geometric Nonlinear Analysis, Multiscale Computation, Co-rotational Method

ABSTRACT

In this work, an efficient multiscale computational formulation is developed for the geometric nonlinear analysis of heterogeneous piezoelectric materials. In this formulation, the relations between the microscopic heterogeneous properties and macroscopic behaviors of the piezoelectric composite are established by the numerically constructed displacement and electric potential base functions. The heterogeneous and complex microstructure can be equivalent to a simple macroscopic piezoelectric coarse element through those constructed multiscale base functions. Then the equivalent tangent stiffness matrix and internal force vector of the macroscopic coarse element are deduced based on the co-rotational approach, which can describe the motion of macroscopic coarse element clearly and efficiently. Thus the original electro-mechanical coupling geometric nonlinear problem could be solved iteratively on the macroscopic scale, which will save a tremendous amount of computing time and cost. After all the macroscopic calculations, the microscopic mechanical and electrical responses could be retrieved and calculated from the macroscopic solutions by using the above-mentioned multiscale shape functions. To verify the validation and high-efficiency of the proposed multiscale computation formulation, several typical numerical examples are carried out. All the computation results indicate that the developed multiscale formulation not only could provide high precision solutions but also has high efficiency.

An example is presented herein to verify the validation and efficiency of the proposed multiscale computational method. The solutions obtained from this multiscale method are compared with the FEM reference ones which are calculated on the fine scale mesh by the standard finite element method. The plane stress state is considered here and all the models have unit thickness. Furthermore, the FEM reference solution is obtained on the fine-scale mesh and denoted by 'PFEM-F', while the multiscale solutions obtained based on the linear, oversampling and periodic boundary conditions are denoted by 'PEMsC-L', 'PEMsC-O' and 'PEMsC-P', respectively.

In order to show the general functionality of the proposed multiscale method, an electro-active bimorph with porous microstructure is analyzed. In Figure 1, the geometry and its boundary conditions, as well as the sub-grids of the unit cell and material properties used are depicted. The dimensions of structure are $L=150\text{mm}$ and $H=4\text{mm}$, and the model is meshed into 150×4 coarse elements. The bimorph consists of two layers connected through an electrode which is located between the two layers, and another electrode is attached at the bottom of the bimorph. The electric boundary conditions are set as zero electric potential at the lower electrode and the potential at the upper edge is left free. An 18kV electric potential which is divided into 20 steps is applied at the middle electrode. The mechanical boundary conditions are prescribed that the left end of the structure is fixed in X direction and the lower left corner is fixed in both X and Y directions. The volume fraction of porosity is 10% and the poling direction is parallel to the positive Y-axis.

Figure 1. Electric bimorph cantilever: (a) Geometry and its boundary conditions; (b) Sub-grids of the unit cell and material properties

Figure 2. Step-wise configuration of the bimorph cantilever under different applied electric potentials together with deformed exemplary unit cell at the free end

As the applied electric potential at the middle electrode increasing, the configuration of the bimorph beam and the deformed exemplary microstructure are shown in Figure 2. There are clearly a macroscopic clockwise bending and a contraction of the microstructure in the direction perpendicular to the electric field. That is because an electric field in the thickness direction is induced in the lower half (active layer) of the bimorph due to the potential difference between the two electrodes. The induced electric field is in the opposite direction to the material polarization, which resulting in the local contraction of the active layer. However, the upper layer is not electrically activated it acts as a passive layer and restrains the lateral deformation of active layer. Thus, bending of the beam is observed. Besides, the unit cell at the free end has performed nearly a full rotation in the final stage of loading. This is due to the slender geometry of the beam, although the local deformations of the unit cell are rather small, the overall rotation of the structure can be very large. This also demonstrates that the proposed nonlinear computational method is able to handle the structure with extreme large rotation.

Figure 3. Tip displacements and rotation vs. applied electric potential

The multiscale solutions ‘PEMsC-P’ have a higher accuracy than ‘PEMsC-L’ and ‘PEMsC-O’. The maximum relative errors of ‘PEMsC-L’, ‘PEMsC-O’ and ‘PEMsC-P’ are 8.9%, 5.5% and 4.1%, respectively. This indicates that the periodic boundary condition should be more suitable than the other ones for heterogeneous piezoelectric materials with periodic microstructure. Figure 3 depicts the normalized tip displacements and rotation of the bimorph versus the applied electric potential. It can be seen from the comparison that the multiscale solutions are in good agreement with the reference ones, which also illustrates the validity of the proposed computational method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The supports of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (11402178), the Hubei Provincial Natural Science Foundation (2014CFB336) and the China Postdoctoral Science Foundation (2015T80831) are gratefully acknowledged.